

Makhmudova Aziza Azamatovna

Faculty of National Dress and Art, Termiz State University Organization of culture and art institutions and 3rd year management course student

Abstract: This article provides information on management decisions. In the proper organization of the activities of cultural and art institutions, it is important that management decisions are made with a focus on specific and targeted issues. Management decisions are a process that involves the preparation of necessary documents, that is, a decision, an order, a plan of actions, and the development, adoption and implementation of relevant decisions.

Key words: culture, art, institution, activity, organization, management, decision, document, order, acceptance, event, plan, process, stage, future, staff, leader, stage, strategic, formal, information.

In the proper organization of the activities of cultural and art institutions, it is important that management decisions are made with a focus on specific and targeted issues. Management decisions are a process that involves the preparation of necessary documents, that is, a decision, an order, a plan of actions, and the development, adoption and implementation of relevant decisions.

Management decisions are classified according to the following symptoms:

- by stages of the period of residence of the commodity;•by systems of the management system;
- by field of activity;
- by Scope;
- on the organization of production;
- by Types and quantity of goals;
- by duration of action (strategic, tactical, operational);
- by task execution;
- by impact objects;
- by formality (formal and informal);
- on information used;
- by reflection forms;
- by decision-making levels;
- by degree of categorization;
- by content (environmental, social, organizational, scientific, technical, etc.k.);
- in terms of depth of exposure (single-stage, multi-stage);
- in the direction of the decision (within or outside the organization);
- by the person making the decision (individual or group);
- by degree of compulsion (Strictly and by nature of recommendation)

The adoption of decisions determines the present and future of the organization. Knowledge and experience are required to make the right decisions, and understanding also plays a major role in this. It includes foresight, imagination, ingenuity. Very often, experienced leaders, having made the right decision, find it difficult to explain how they did it. Decision making and

implementation is a complex process that consists of several steps, which includes the following steps:

- * problem recognition;
- * problem formulation;
- * setting criteria for solving the problem, goal.

Identifying a problem and forming it correctly requires a lot of skill from the manager. He must distinguish the most important and significant from them, without planning to solve all the problems in a row.

Two types in determining the criteria for a successful decision –in the case of” We must “and” we want”, criteria are selected. In the second case, the desired goals are considered. Decision making the process is made up of the following steps:

- * development of alternatives;
- * evaluation of alternatives;
- * selection of alternatives.

Many alternative decisions are known from previous experience. But often unique problems arise. In this case, a creative approach is necessary. There are the following methods of searching for alternatives: “mental attack”, promotion of proposals, Group analysis of the situation, a cause-and-effect diagram, a thought card. All identified alternatives must be compared and evaluated. Their assessment provides for the identification of negative and creative aspects with the help of quantitative and quality meters. Implementation of comparison of alternative options for decisions for they must be brought to a comparable appearance according to one or another criterion. Nevertheless, alternative options differ by one or another criterion. The task is to ensure that they are compared by a larger amount of criteria. Modeling is an important aspect of coordination of management decisions, which in turn is based on logical, physical and economic-mathematical calculations. On the basis of logical modeling lies the analysis of the factors that determine the choice of decision. Physical models will consist of natural objects that are proportionally reduced several times and made of different materials. They are made in a scaled-down form with the aim of saving materials to verify aesthetic, bottling and other definitions of the object. When conducting an experiment, one or more alternatives are checked in practice. Conducting research and analysis is an ideologically effective way to assemble alternatives. It provides for the solution of the problem based on the search for its most important variability, limitations and interrelationships between its bases, and the separation of the problem into organizational parts and its study. Computers are used in the development of various models of tiles.

Execution of the decision includes:

- * Organization of execution of the decision;
- * establish control over the execution of the decision;
- * assessment of activities for the implementation of the decision.

The organization of the implementation of the decision provides for the Coordination of the actions of many people. The manager should encourage people to follow the decision. To do this, it is necessary to develop measures for the implementation of the decision, to take into account the rights and obligations among the participants, the effective use of their abilities, and to build a communication network for the exchange of information, to regulate relations between participants, to coordinate their interests. It is also necessary to develop a mechanism for creating

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-4

a database of information that receives a system of finding errors and achievements, including in the implementation of the decision. This in turn allows you to correct erroneous actions. Based on the information received from the sources, the problems and their solutions are correctly evaluated and the manager's solution to the problem

there will be an opportunity to show interest to employees.

REFERENCES

1. Makhmudova, A. (2018). Ensuring the competitiveness of the scientific approaches of eco-tourism a case of Uzbekistan. *South Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research*, 8(11), 33-41.
2. Makhmudova, A. (2019). Enhancement of the Ecotourism Efficiency in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Experience of the Developed Countries. *Indonesian Journal of Law and Economics Review*, 3.
3. Wikipedia
4. Arxiv.uz

C M R T